

Management

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**Human performance management systems in hybrid and remote work
environments**

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Abstract. The **purpose of this study** is to examine contemporary approaches and models of personnel productivity management across traditional, hybrid, and remote work formats, to identify their strengths and constraints, and to develop recommendations for their practical application in organizations. Results are expected to improve the quality of management decisions and contribute to higher productivity outcomes. **Methods.** The study employed systematic and comparative analysis of scientific literature, content analysis of publications of Ukrainian and foreign scholars, and a structural-functional approach to evaluate productivity management models. The study investigates the relationships and dependencies among organizational, technological, and psychological factors that shape employee productivity in traditional, hybrid, and remote work formats. The **study's results** showed that a high level of direct control and organizational discipline characterizes traditional work formats. At the same time, hybrid and remote models require more flexible approaches to management, focusing on employee self-organization, the

availability of digital platforms and motivational systems that consider the psychological and social needs of personnel. It was found that the effective use of technological tools, such as analytical productivity systems, communication platforms and artificial intelligence for personnel management, allows to increase productivity and optimize processes. However, the integration of psychological well-being, motivational strategies, and strengthening of corporate culture in remote and hybrid work environments remains largely overlooked. **Conclusions.** Based on the analysis, recommendations were developed to improve productivity management systems, balancing performance monitoring, motivational approaches, and employee engagement, while considering the conditions of flexible work formats and digital technologies. The practical significance of the study is reflected in the potential application of its results to the development of corporate strategies aimed at enhancing labor efficiency, optimizing personnel management processes, and supporting organizational adaptation to evolving work models, as well as serving as a foundation for further research in the field of personnel productivity management under conditions of digitalization and changing forms of labor organization.

Keywords: labor productivity, hybrid work, remote work, personnel management, motivation, technological tools, organizational factors, psychological aspects.

**Системи управління продуктивністю персоналу в умовах гібридних і
віддалених форматів роботи**

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Анотація. Метою дослідження є комплексний аналіз сучасних підходів та моделей управління продуктивністю персоналу в традиційних, гібридних та дистанційних форматах роботи, а також визначення їхніх переваг і обмежень з метою підвищення ефективності управлінських рішень та формування рекомендацій для практичного впровадження в організаціях. **Методи.** Дослідження проводилось із використанням методів системного та порівняльного аналізу наукових джерел, контент-аналізу публікацій українських і зарубіжних авторів, а також структурно-функціонального підходу до оцінки моделей управління продуктивністю. Особливу увагу приділено вивченню взаємодії організаційних, технологічних та психологічних чинників, що впливають на продуктивність працівників у різних форматах роботи. **Результати** дослідження показали, що традиційні формати праці характеризуються високим рівнем прямого контролю та організаційної дисципліни, тоді як гібридні та дистанційні моделі вимагають більш гнучких підходів до управління, акцентуючи увагу на самоорганізації працівників, доступності цифрових платформ та системах мотивації, що враховують психологічні та соціальні потреби персоналу. Виявлено, що ефективне використання технологічних інструментів, таких як аналітичні системи продуктивності, комунікаційні платформи та штучний інтелект для управління персоналом, дозволяє підвищити продуктивність та оптимізувати процеси, однак відмічається недостатнє опрацювання питань інтеграції психологічного благополуччя, мотиваційних стратегій та підтримки корпоративної культури у віддаленому та гібридному середовищі. **Висновки.** На основі проведеного аналізу сформульовано рекомендації щодо вдосконалення систем управління продуктивністю, які передбачають баланс між контролем результатів, мотиваційними програмами та залученістю співробітників, з урахуванням специфіки гнучких форматів роботи та цифрових інструментів. Практична значущість дослідження полягає у можливості використання його результатів для розробки корпоративних

стратегій підвищення ефективності праці, оптимізації процесів управління персоналом та адаптації організацій до трансформацій робочих моделей, а також для подальших наукових досліджень у сфері управління продуктивністю персоналу за умов цифровізації та зміни форм організації праці.

Ключові слова: продуктивність праці, гібридна робота, дистанційна робота, управління персоналом, мотивація, технологічні інструменти, організаційні фактори, психологічні аспекти.

Problem statement. In today's digitalization and rapidly evolving market dynamics, organizations are facing new challenges in ensuring effective personnel management. The COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the transition to hybrid and remote work formats, fundamentally reshaping traditional approaches to labor organization, productivity oversight, and employee motivation. However, performance management systems originally designed for the office-based formats often lack adaptability, leading to reduced efficiency in human resource use, communication, and difficulties evaluating outcomes.

Although scientific research offers diverse approaches to performance management, most remain focused on traditional models, insufficiently addressing specifics of remote work, particularly its psychological dimensions and the demand for flexible motivational tools. This highlights the necessity of developing adaptable performance management systems that effectively balance control, autonomy, and motivation within hybrid and remote work environments.

Therefore, performance management in emerging work formats represents a critical challenge for both research and practice, as workforce efficiency directly influences organizational competitiveness and long-term sustainability.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Analysis of scientific sources indicates that managing personnel productivity in hybrid and remote environments is a critical issue in contemporary management, which is evolving rapidly under the

influence of digitalization and socio-economic changes. O. Bekhter [1] considers the impact of a hybrid environment on the effectiveness of personnel management, emphasizing the importance of managers' adaptation to new models of control, motivation and involvement, but provides a limited analysis of psychological aspects, in particular stress resistance and self-organization. Yu. V. Aranovych, P. I. Sokurenko, O. V. Valentiieva, L. D. Chalapko [2] explores innovative approaches to motivating and retaining talent, emphasizing personalized incentive systems and the role of corporate culture; however, issues of technological tools for controlling productivity remain insufficiently explored. V. A. Nesteruk [3] identifies key success factors: effective communication, access to digital platforms and staff self-organization, noting that remote work expands personnel opportunities but creates risks of reducing discipline, which requires new performance assessment systems. K. O. Skibska [4] emphasizes the importance of artificial intelligence and data analytics in predicting productivity and optimizing processes but has a limited view of their impact on employee motivation and psychological aspects. N. M. Karpenko and O. Ye. Halan [5] investigate factors and stages of productivity management, emphasizing the importance of innovative technologies and structural changes, as well as the need to balance control, motivation, and involvement. However, psychological dimensions of remote work remain insufficiently explored. O. M. Ivakhnenko [6] identifies material, organizational, economic, natural and socio-psychological factors of labor productivity, emphasizing working and leisure conditions, but overlooking the specific characteristics of the hybrid work environment. I. V. Dvornyk [7] classifies factors into organizational-economic, technical-economic, socio-economic and natural-climatic categories. However, the role of technologies and digital platforms in shaping remote productivity remains insufficiently addressed. N. M. Makhnachova and I. Yu. Semeniuk [8] analyze the complex impact of material-technical, economic-legal, socio-psychological, and motivational factors, emphasizing the importance for an integrated approach to personnel management; however, aspects of flexible working hours and online

interaction remain insufficiently explored. V. M. Honcharov [9] analyzes macro-level factors of productivity across various levels, yet the interrelation between organizational and psychological aspects in a hybrid environment remains unexplored. S. E. Kuchina and R. G. Maistro [10] consider technological and organizational tools for increasing productivity; at the same time, psychological aspects and motivational strategies for remote workers remain inefficiently addressed. D. Zahirniak, V. Druzhinina and V. Druzhinin [11] consider remote work as a current management trend highlighting its role in enhancing flexibility and adaptability of enterprises; at the same time, analysis remains confined to general organizational aspects and lacks a detailed examination of the legal framework. O. Lutsenko [12] investigates legal aspects of remote work in martial law, emphasizing the need to adapt labor legislation to emergency conditions, practical recommendations for employers remain unspecified. Yu. Yu. Ivchuk [13] conducts a comparative analysis of international practices in remote employment and prospects for their legal regulation in Ukraine, emphasizing the importance of aligning with global standards; however, the question of the economic efficiency of such employment models remains insufficiently explored. S. Vyshnovetska and V. Kolonska [14] focus on the organizational and legal aspects of remote work during martial law, emphasizing the risks of violation of labor rights and the need to develop adaptive management models. A. Danilkova, Ye. Shelest and T. Glushko [15] investigate organization of remote work under quarantine restrictions, focusing on the practical aspects of formalizing labor relations and maintaining personnel productivity. The impact of psychological factors on work efficiency remains an open area for research.

Identification of previously unresolved parts of the general problem.

Despite extensive research on personnel productivity management, several critical aspects of hybrid and remote formats require deeper investigation. Most existing systems are rooted in traditional office models based on direct supervision and regular in-person interaction, which fail to take into account psychological and

social dimensions of remote work, the significance of employee autonomy, and the risks of declining motivation. Moreover, the literature pays limited attention to the integration of digital tools for productivity monitoring and analytics; often examining individual technology in isolation rather than through a comprehensive framework that captures both individual and team performance. The research gap can be attributed to the relatively recent large-scale adoption of hybrid formats and the fact that much of the earlier work had been conducted before the COVID-19 pandemic or was limited to local contexts. Addressing these issues demands the interdisciplinary approach that integrates psychological, organizational and technological perspectives, thereby increasing the complexity of research. Confronting these issues is essential to design effective performance management systems capable of balancing control, motivation, and employee engagement. The study seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of existing systems in hybrid environments, identify key psychological and organizational factors influencing remote teams productivity, and propose recommendations for the integration of digital tools to enhance management efficiency. It aims to contribute to the practical and applicable model of personnel productivity management suited to modern working conditions.

Formulation of the article's objectives (task statement). The purpose of this article is to conduct a comprehensive examination of personnel productivity management systems in hybrid and remote work formats, identifying practical approaches and to develop recommendations for their adaptation to current organizational conditions.

To achieve this goal, the study sets following objectives:

1. To analyze existing approaches and models of personnel productivity management in traditional and remote work modalities, identifying their advantages and constraints.
2. To determine key factors and tools influencing employee productivity in hybrid and remote formats, with particular attention to psychological, organizational, and technological aspects.

3. To develop evidence-based recommendations for enhancing performance management systems that ensure a balance between performance monitoring, employee motivation, and engagement.

Presentation of the main research material. Effective adaptation to a hybrid work environments requires managers to acquire new competencies and implement strategies for managing core processes. Therefore, it is necessary to provide employees with the appropriate resources and timely information to support daily operations. Such support should include not only regular project status monitoring and updates, but also access to the documents and digital tools utilized by the team [1, p. 3]. Another challenge of hybrid format lies in sustaining corporate culture, which remains a key determinant of team cohesion. Addressing this issue calls for the creation of opportunities for collaboration and collective activities in virtual settings. Examples include regular online meetings, video conferences, and virtual teambuildings or corporate events, all of which strengthen emotional connection and reinforce employees' sense of belonging [2, p. 91]. Equally important is the quality of the home work environment, which significantly affects employee productivity and well-being.

With access to the quiet and properly equipped workspace, employees productivity can improve significantly. For instance, a study of the Tempo call center shows that remote employees processed calls more efficiently as they were not affected by the background noise common in open offices. Furthermore, remote work broadens an organization's human resource potential by enabling recruitment of specialists from different regions and countries without the need for physical relocation [3, p. 135].

Current development of human resources management (HR) is largely shaped by the consequences of the pandemic and armed conflicts, which have triggered extensive digital and organizational transformations. Key dimensions of this process include greater attention to employees well-being, strengthening the role of HR specialists within organizational structures, automation of recruitment processes,

and application of the artificial intelligence both for talent acquisition and for the effective management of the existing personnel. The majority of current HR trends are directly linked to the digital transformation, which is being actively implemented by companies worldwide [4, p. 109]. Following the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine, a decline in labor productivity has been observed. Under these circumstances, management processes aimed at regulating and stimulating productivity growth within enterprises acquire particular significance [5, p. 8].

Personnel productivity management has long been a cornerstone of organizational effectiveness, as employee engagement and performance directly determine the achievement of strategic goals. Traditional approaches to productivity management were developed over decades relying on hierarchical models of labor organization, a clear division of responsibilities and direct managerial control. Over time, these approaches incorporated tools such as the Management by Objectives, competency-based assessment, the KPI system, and the Balanced Scorecard. These instruments facilitated the establishment of transparent productivity metrics and their alignment with the organizational strategy. The effectiveness of these largely depended on employees' physical presence and continuous monitoring of their activities. A comparison of traditional in-person and remote approaches to performance management highlights fundamental differences in control mechanisms, motivational practices, and performance evaluation methods (table 1).

Table 1

Comparison of traditional and remote approaches to personnel performance management

Characteristics	Traditional models	Remote models
Orientation	Focus on processes and task execution	Focus on outcomes and goal achievement
Control	Direct supervision, regular monitoring	Indirect management, trust-based, supported by digital tools
Core tools	KPI, Balanced Scorecard, competency assessment	OKR, project management platforms, data analytics
Flexibility	Low-oriented toward stability	High-adaptive and responsive to change

Characteristics	Traditional models	Remote models
Communications	Predominantly offline, formal meetings	Online platforms, video conferencing, corporate chats, synchronous/asynchronous communication channels
Employee role	Dependent, performance accountable to management	Autonomous, self-directed contributor oriented toward result
Well-being	Clear separation between professional and personal domains	Blurred boundaries requiring organizational support to safeguard well-being and prevent burnout
Motivation and engagement	Driven by pay, bonuses, and recognition, with engagement reinforced through daily in-person contact	Built on belonging, shared goals, and recognition, with engagement supported by trust, clarity, and digital collaboration
Culture and belonging	Fostered through daily in-person interactions, shared office routines, and workplace traditions	Supported by regular virtual meetings, online team activities, and communication practices that encourage collaboration and connection

Source: author's development

As can be seen from the data in Table 1, remote models are primarily oriented toward goal achievement, offering greater flexibility and autonomy, whereas traditional models remain focused on processes, task performance, and formal control mechanisms. At the same time, both approaches have their limitations. For traditional models the problem lies in their conservatism, tendency towards excessive bureaucratization, and dependence on the physical presence of employees. For remote teams, risks include reduced team cohesion, challenges in maintaining corporate culture, and the need for substantial investments in digital technologies. These differences reflect a broader shift in orientation from process-driven structures to outcome-based systems.

A significant advantage of remote models is the ability to attract employees from diverse regions and countries, thereby increasing the personnel flexibility of organizations. At the same time, this approach requires a well-developed system of communication and support, as employees may experience psychological isolation, weakened connection to corporate culture, and limited interaction with colleagues. This highlights the importance of addressing well-being and work-life balance, since blurred boundaries in remote work can heighten stress and diminish engagement.

Consequently, the development of new tools to strengthen team dynamics in virtual environments becomes particularly relevant.

Special attention should be given to the integration of digital technologies into performance management systems, particularly the use of platforms for online task monitoring, digital tools for assessing results, and electronic reporting systems. In remote work conditions digital transformation provides mechanisms for monitoring, enhances the accuracy of evaluation, and supports timely adjustments to work processes, making it a crucial driver of efficiency. Project management platforms such as Asana, Trello, and Jira enable real-time tracking of tasks and overall workflow transparency. Productivity analytics tools provide objective data on workloads and outcomes. At the same time, technological dependence may create risks when digital culture and competencies are insufficient, underscoring the connection between organizational and psychological readiness for digital work.

Another critical aspect is employees motivation and engagement in different work modalities. In traditional settings, motivation is largely shaped by material incentives and direct managerial interaction, while engagement is reinforced through daily presence and in-person collaboration. In remote modality motivation is grounded in the sense of belonging, shared goals, trust, and recognition of contributions while engagement is sustained on clear communication, regular feedback, and consistent participation in digital collaboration.

Differences are also evident in performance assessment. Traditional approaches emphasize periodic evaluations, often quarterly or annually, which are sufficient for retrospective analysis, but are not effective in rapidly changing environments. Remote models prioritize continuous feedback and flexible assessment tools that enable timely adjustments and maintain employee motivation. At the same time, remote format place greater responsibility on employees for self-management, which may foster autonomy but may also increase stress if organizational support is insufficient.

In conclusion, both traditional and remote performance management models have distinct advantages and constraints. Traditional approaches remain effective for direct supervision (table 2), structured communication, stable routines, and clear role definitions, but they rely heavily on physical presence and hierarchical control. Remote approaches, by contrast, provide flexibility, broaden access to talent across regions, and foster innovation through digitalization. They also require deliberate support to sustain motivation, ensure well-being, and preserve corporate culture.

Table 2

Advantages and limitations of traditional and remote performance management models

Model type	Advantages	Constraints
Traditional	Clear structure, defined roles, alignment with the corporate strategy and culture	Low flexibility, bureaucratic, reliant on physical presence, slow adoption of changes
Remote	Flexible and adaptive, driven by data and results, broader talent pool, digital integration	Risk of isolation; fragile corporate culture; high tech and competency demands

Source: author's development

A comparison of traditional and remote models of personnel productivity management highlights their distinct organizational features, which determine the suitability in different contexts. Traditional approaches are most effective for organizations operating in highly stable environments. Remote models demonstrate greater efficiency under conditions of dynamic change and increased demand for flexibility. The most appropriate solution to address current challenges is the development of hybrid management systems that integrate structural clarity of the traditional models with the adaptability and technological capacities of remote models.

Ukrainian scholars emphasize a wide range of factors influencing labor productivity at the enterprise level. These are commonly classified into organizational, technological, motivational, and psychological categories, which

together provide a comprehensive framework for assessing the effectiveness of personnel management (table 3).

Table 3

Classification of labor productivity factors in Ukrainian scholarly research

Author	Definition of labor productivity factors
O. M. Ivakhnenko [6, p. 45]	- material and technical; organizational and economic and managerial; natural; socio-economic; socio-psychological (working and leisure conditions)
I. V. Dvornyk [7, p. 247–248]	- organizational and economic; technical and economic; socio-economic; natural and climatic
N. M. Makhnachova, I. Yu. Semeniuk [8, p. 305]	- material and technical; economic, legal and regulatory; socio-psychological; organizational and economic and structural; material and stimulating
V. M. Honcharov [9, p. 34]	- internal production; industry and inter-industry; regional; national
S. E. Kuchina, R. G. Maistro [10, p. 38]	- increase in the technical level of production; improvement of the organization of production and labor; increase in production volume; structural changes in production; influence of natural conditions

Source: systematized by the author

The evolution of personnel productivity management systems emphasizes the necessity for continuous improvement and adaptation to changing work conditions. Further research in this area should prioritize development of hybrid models that balance control with trust, structure with flexibility, and technological support with the sustainment of corporate culture. Such approach creates opportunities for innovative methods to productivity management that address the needs of both organizations and employees in an increasingly dynamic global environment.

The spread of remote work reflects ongoing transformations in the global economy and a gradual shift away from traditional models of labor organization. Although numerous definitions of this phenomenon appear in the literature, several common conditions can be identified: the systematic performance of work tasks, the implementation of professional activities outside the employer's premises, and the active use of modern information and communication technologies to organize and support labor processes [11, p. 4]. Remote work offers important advantages for both employees and employers. For employees it provides the opportunity to perform

professional tasks in a comfortable environment, while retaining the right to fair compensation. For employers, it reduces costs and obligations associated with maintaining physical workspaces as the responsibility for safe working conditions during remote work largely rests with employees [12, p. 30].

Employee productivity in hybrid and remote work formats is a multidimensional phenomenon shaped by several interrelated factors. In this context, the study of key aspects that determine work effectiveness under conditions of digital transformation is becoming increasingly relevant. Remote work, which was once perceived as an exception, has now become a common practice, while the hybrid format has emerged as a compromise between traditional office interaction and opportunities offered by digital technologies, but also a necessity shaped by external circumstances such as COVID-19 pandemic, armed conflicts, migration processes, which have compelled organizations to adopt flexible models to sustain operations. This brings not only advantages but also challenges that require careful analysis. The benefits of remote work include flexible schedules, broader staffing opportunities, reduced office space costs, and higher employee satisfaction. At the same time, challenges include risks to sustain employee motivation and self-discipline, difficulties in communication and team coordination, the ongoing need to modernize digital platforms, and the requirement to strengthen employees' digital literacy. This balance of benefits and challenges highlights the necessity of adaptive performance management systems and comprehensive performance assessment strategies. As illustrated in Table 4, key factors and tools influencing employee productivity in hybrid and remote formats include effective communication, access to digital platforms, motivational systems, and performance assessment mechanisms. The data below compares incentive and control methods across different organizational conditions, demonstrating the need for an integrated approach to performance management in hybrid and remote models.

Table 4

Key factors and instruments influencing employee productivity in hybrid and remote work formats

Aspect	Key factors	Tools for influencing
Psychological	Motivation; risk of burnout; emotional resilience; sense of team belonging	Psychological support educational programs; regular online communications; virtual team-building activities
Organizational	Tasks clarity; effective communication; corporate culture; performance evaluation system	Task management systems; goal setting methodologies, structured regular feedback; flexible work schedules; corporate online events
Technological	Employee digital literacy; accessibility of tools; information security; effectiveness of technical solutions and processes	Project management platforms; video conferencing; cloud services; cyber protection systems, integration of AI to learning systems, creating feedback loops

Source: author's development

Thus, productivity in hybrid and remote formats is determined by the multifactorial interaction of psychological, organizational and technological factors. Their combination forms a unique environment where labor efficiency depends on the consistency of actions between the employee and the employer, the company's ability to provide the necessary conditions to support the motivation and performance of personnel, as well as on the level of digital capabilities and security. Successful management of these aspects creates the prerequisites for the sustainable development of the organization and the formation of competitive advantages in the modern dynamic environment.

Remote work is defined as a modern form of labor organization enabled by information and communication technologies, characterized by the employee's workplace being located outside the employer's office. The integration of remote work into enterprises, institutions and organizations allows employees greater autonomy in planning their working time, increases flexibility in production process, and supports productivity even under adverse conditions such as quarantine restrictions, emergencies, or martial law [13, p. 119].

Remote work is characterized by remote interaction, flexible scheduling, reliance on digital collaboration tools, limited physical contact, task performance at a distance, the requirement of specialized technical equipment, and a heightened demand for self-discipline. At the same time, it creates significant advantages for both employees and employers [14, p. 155]. Employees productivity is primarily determined by their ability to self-organize. In a traditional office environment (in person), it is easier for employees to concentrate on completing tasks and adhere to a set work schedule. In contrast, working remotely often weakens discipline and can negatively affect work results [15, p. 6].

A systematic approach to enhancing productivity requires the interrelated influence of psychological, organizational and technological factors. Psychological dimension encompasses the development of self-organization, stress management and the establishment of a supportive motivational environment. Organizational measures focus on optimizing work processes, clarifying roles and responsibilities, ensuring transparency in performance evaluation, and fostering employee engagement. Technological solutions provide the basis for uninterrupted communication, task monitoring, and efficiency analysis. Coordinated implementation of these three dimensions makes it possible to build a sustainable performance management system that aligns individual needs of employees with the strategic objectives of the organization.

Key recommendations for improving performance management systems, balancing control, motivation, and employee engagement are presented in Table 5.

Table 5

Recommendations for improving personnel performance management systems

Direction	Recommendations	Expected effect
Goal setting	Establish clear and measurable objectives, link individual goals with organizational strategy, ensure transparency in goal communication	Align employee efforts with strategic priorities, improved clarity and accountability
Results control	Implementation of flexible performance assessment systems, regular feedback, and a combination combine of	More accurate evaluation; timely adjustments to processes, reduced risk of demotivation. Increasing

Direction	Recommendations	Expected effect
	quantitative and qualitative indicators, introduce regular feedback cycles	the accuracy of assessment, reducing the risk of demotivation, and timely adjustment of processes
Motivation	More accurate evaluation, timely adjustments to processes, reduced risk of demotivation	Increased commitment to results, higher efficiency and job satisfaction
Engagement	Engage employees in decision-making; foster virtual collaboration and team events, reinforce corporate culture digitally	Stronger sense of belonging; improved cohesion, lower turnover
Processes	Standardize workflows, optimize communication channels, ensure clarity in task distribution and accountability	Streamlined operations, minimized duplication, improved coordination in distributed teams
Technologies	Use project management platforms, digital reporting, automation, and productivity analytics, ensure data security and digital literacy, Integrate AI instruments for repetitive processes	Greater transparency, reduced workload, adaptability to hybrid/remote formats

Source: author's development

The improvement of personnel productivity management systems in remote and hybrid organizations should be based on balanced interaction of psychological, organizational, and technological factors. The application of comprehensive approaches that integrate these dimensions increases work efficiency, supports professional development of employees, and ensures the sustainability of organizations in conditions of dynamic change.

Conclusions. The conducted study has systematized existing approaches to personnel productivity management and identified principal psychological, organizational, and technological factors influencing employee efficiency. It was demonstrated that flexible evaluation systems with integration of material and non-material incentives, and established mechanisms of employee participation in organizational processes are essential for achieving a balance between control, motivation, and engagement.

The analysis confirmed limited applicability of traditional productivity management methods in hybrid and remote work formats. The introduction of digital platforms, automated task monitoring, and analytical tools enhances transparency

and ensures timely feedback. the maintenance of employees wellbeing and development of their self-organization remain decisive conditions for sustained performance.

The results confirm the need for performance management models that integrate organizational, technological, and psychological dimensions within a unified framework. Such models enhance efficiency, facilitate professional development, and contribute to organizational resilience under conditions of structural and environmental changes. Further research could examine the dependency between individual employee characteristics and their productivity outcome, and refine methodological approaches to the design of adaptive systems for hybrid work formats.

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